

Market economy and the emergence of social and gender inequality among Jakun Orang Asli

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Abstract

Despite Malaysia's economic emergence, Orang Asli communities remain among the poorest in the country. Multiple factors are responsible for this situation and result in an important impact on their life. The Jakun village of Kampung Peta (Mersing, Johor) has been surveyed three times between the 1960s and 1999. The goal of my own study was to measure the effect of the development of a market economy on the village's economic and social life. In 2019, at the time of my survey, the village of Kampung Peta is still benefiting from good material and social conditions: a pristine environment, a national park nearby offering the resources of tourism, and a strong collective leadership. Are these favourable conditions sufficient to shift securely from subsistence economy to market economy? In order to understand the economic opportunities, dreams and constraints of the Jakun of Kampung Peta, I surveyed the sources of income of the whole village and more precisely the incomes of fifteen households of various socio-economic status, based on their declarations during qualitative interviews. As formal employment and free-lance economic opportunities outside the primary sector are scarce and women have restricted access to them, my conclusions raise concern regarding the rise of social and gender inequality, as already observed in 1999.

#SocialAnthropology #OrangAsli #RuralEconomy #GenderInequality #Women

Kampung Peta is a village on the river Endau, in northern Johor. Because of its location between Endau-Rompin national park and a forest reserve, the villagers have access to the tourism economy. Peta is home to the Jakun people, a sub-group of the Melayu Asli or indigenous Malays, also present in southern Pahang. Travellers and scientists documented the way of life and social organisation of the Jakun: J. R. Logan (1847), P. É. L. Favre (1865), D. F. A. Hervey (1879 and 1881), H. W. Lake and H. J. Kelsall (1894), W. W. Skeat and C. O. Blagden (1906), and I. H. N. Evans (1923). Then in the mid-1960s, Maeda Narifumi produced an ethnography of the whole Endau River basin, Kampung Peta being the village with the most upstream location. Colin Nicholas studied this village in 1999 and Shanthi Thambiah published in 1999 an ethnographic study of three Jakun villages sharing family ties: Pengkalan Tereh in Kluang, Kampung Punan and Kampung Peta, Mersing. My research benefited from the existence of this documentation and allowed me to observe and make comparisons as well. In the spring of 2019, I started an ethnographic survey in Kampung Peta, as part of the requirements for my Master of Arts diploma from the School for Advanced Studies in Social Sciences (EHESS, Paris, France) under the supervision of Pr. Bernard Sellato.

1. STRUCTURAL CHANGE IN THE ECONOMY OF A JAKUN VILLAGE

Commercial activities, in this case the collection of non-timber forest products, have been documented since the first millennium in the peninsula (Andaya 2002: 30) and more specifically trade by the Jakun of the Endau basin (Logan 1847: 261). In spite of their long history in this trade, the Orang Asli have until recently depended mostly on a subsistence economy. Their transition to a mainly market economy is well documented, with texts that cover several decades and concern several groups: Jakun in the 1960s (Maeda 2001), Batek in the 1970s (Endicott and Endicott 2012), Semai in the 1980s (Gomes 2004) and Temuan in the 1990s (Nobuta 2009). These studies reflect very different situations and a greater or lesser dependence on commercial activities.

From the 1960s to 1999, the social structures of the Jakun of Kampung Peta changed at a very fast pace. Swidden agriculture, still documented by Naeda, disappeared under the combined effects of the shrinking area of agricultural lands conceded to the village by the authorities, de facto prohibiting this type of agriculture, and of the availability of cheap rice from northern Malaysia. In 1999 these villagers had already abandoned subsistence agriculture, hunting and

fishing: their economy consisted in the collection of rattan, in commercial crops (mainly rubber), and was completed by wage employment in nearby plantations, the logging industry, tourism or government positions (Thambiah 1999: 276-279).

In 2019, the villagers participate strongly in the market economy. Rattan and rubber still offer the most accessible income. Other activities allow the villagers to earn a living, either through self-employment or salaried work. Retail trade and handicraft are the main forms of self-employment. The majority of employment is in the public sector. Other opportunities for the villagers exist outside the village, at the nearby plantation and even further, in the town of Kahang, the *pekan* closest to Kampung Peta. Kahang is still far enough to prevent the workers from returning home each night. Tourism, regardless of the form of employment, is the most emblematic economic activity in Kampung Peta, the one that ensures the highest individual income.

An initial survey of each house, carried out with the help of my informant and hostess Asma¹, allowed me to list the activities of household members and the proportion of each activity in the village: collection of forest products, agriculture, tourism employment and other jobs. I was able to verify and confirm the accuracy of this information through the interviews I conducted subsequently with about 15 nuclear families or *kelamin*. The *kelamin* is the unit in which the Jakun live and share resources. It is an economic and, ideally, a residential unit. Yet, it is not uncommon for a house or residential unit to be home to several *kelamin*, typically an older couple with a married son or daughter. There are 71 houses in Kampung Peta. Two *kelamin* have two houses, a few houses are vacant and a little more than ten houses are shared by two *kelamin*, occasionally three. That makes a total of around 75 *kelamin* in the village.

Kerja kampung is the most common way to earn a living in a Malaysian village. It is defined by Eric C. Thompson in his ethnographic study of a Malay village in the 1990s as self-entrepreneurship or informal employment in the primary sector or other non-gendered activities specific to rural life (Thompson 2012: 97). It is yet difficult to survey, as it can be a main source of income or a complement of regular wages. As it is a non-gendered activity, it is carried out by both adults of the *kelamin*, which makes it difficult to individualise. I have found that 37 *kelamin* possess rubber plots that are all exploited. Of them, 29 seem to make it their primary source of income. 7 *kelamin* collect rattan: some of them do not own rubber

1 The names in this article have been changed.

plots, some of them do, in only one of them is the man employed. Retail trade is also a family matter. Couples own a shop together, on the side of another activity: rubber farming, but also wage employment. Other self-employed activities can be individualised, like free-lance tour guiding (an activity involving more men than women) or fishing and boat guiding (which are both dependent on the ownership of a boat and appear to be a male prerogative).

	Women	Men	Kelamin	Total
Rubber farming			37	74
Taman Negara	4	15		19
Rattan collection			7	14
Retail trade			6	12
Free-lance tour guiding	3	6		9
Public employment (school included)	5	3		8
Free-lance boat guiding	0	7		7
Oil palm plantation	1	5		6
Fishing and fish trade	0	5		5
Craft	2	1		3
Other private wage employment	0	3		3

Table 1. Income sources in Kampung Peta. My survey, spring 2019.

Formal employment (public employment at Taman Negara and in the village, private employment, mainly at the oil palm plantation) is easier to survey. My survey (see table 2) shows that women and men do not have the same access to formal employment, as 26 men have a steady position and only 10 women. To understand this gap, we must first take into consideration the history of gender division of labour in Jakun social organisation.

2. THE SOURCES OF GENDER DIVISION OF LABOUR

The first texts that we have on the Jakun show a gendered division of labour. Logan made this observation in his study in 1847 (Logan 1847). He observed that women took care of domestic chores and were more involved in reproductive rather than productive activities, unlike men.

In the house (...) the husband appears more as an honored guest than as the lord. The wife has the entire management. A Binuá [Jakun] expressed their ideas on this score figuratively, by saying that the husband was the *nakhoda* of the *práúh* [the skipper of the boat], and the wife *nakhoda* of the house. (Logan 1847: 266)

Maeda confirmed this analysis in 1965.

The division of labor between the sexes is clear. In a house the wife is said to be the skipper and is responsible for household matters, in which the husband hardly interferes. (Maeda 2001: 65)

Women are also in charge of cultivation around the house, as opposed to the more distant rice fields.

Simple gardening may be carried on near the residence, where vegetables, sweet potatoes, banana, sugar cane, bamboo, rubber, and various fruit trees are planted. This work is done entirely by the women. (Maeda 2001: 40)

Shanthi Thambiah qualifies this observation by noting a difference between tasks that are strictly reserved for one gender and tasks that are more commonly performed by either gender.

In food preparation, carrying water and child care, women are more involved than men but these tasks are not exclusively done by women. Washing clothes, collecting firewood and house cleaning are also predominantly done by women, while building and repairing the house is an exclusively male activity. (Thambiah 1999: 280)

This is an important nuance as it reflects a gendered division of labour that is quite flexible and is found in other Orang Asli peoples. Even in the case of highly gendered activities, such as blowpipe hunting, Endicott and Endicott observe among the Batek a participation of women albeit quite low: only 2% of the hunting trips have female participants (Endicott and Endicott 2012: 113-114). This indicates however that they are not prohibited from using a blowpipe or hunting animals.

Other dimensions of the village economy also involve women and men working together: rattan collection and subsistence fishing are activities that Maeda, like Shanthi Thambiah in the late 1990s, saw carried out together by couples. The division between mixed and non-mixed activities is not between subsistence activities (hunting, fishing, agriculture) and commercial activities (rattan collection, wage labour) but within these activities: couples fish and cultivate rice together but it is mainly the men who hunt; couples look for rattan and *kayu tije* (a tree whose pulp is sold for the production of adhesive) together but only the men are wage earners. Shanthi Thambiah nevertheless observed a shift within the activities that were perceived as mixed and noted that rattan collection was becoming more specialized: groups of men organised more efficiently collecting heavier bulks of rattans. The women were not included in these harvests anymore. Since older couples were more likely to work together than younger couples, she wondered whether this was a development that had so far only affected younger couples or whether, having grown older in turn, they would once again enjoy working as a couple. For my part, I have observed couples of all ages (from 30 to 60) collecting rattan together, and women more than men. Rattan is the activity of those who do not have any other choice, and it did not appear to me as specially gendered (except its cleaning, which is done solely by women, but rattan is now usually sold uncleaned).

3. THE RISE OF MONETARY NEEDS

The rise of commercial activities at the expense of subsistence activities, documented by Maeda, has been followed by a rise in wage employment. These changes are due to increased monetary needs and changes in lifestyles and dietary habits.

The Jakun of Kampung Peta have traditionally practised slash-and-burn agriculture, hunting, fishing and collecting forest products for food, medicine or commercial purposes (Maeda 2001: 37-40). Yet, in the 1960s, Maeda notes that “the harvest of dry rice provides subsistence only temporarily” and that “Orang Hulu [Jakun] like to eat the commercial rice from Padang Endau” (Maeda 2001: 40). Today, the share of subsistence farming is even lower and they buy rice, vegetables (eggplant, tomato, cucumber, Chinese cabbage, *bok choy*, dried chilli, garlic and shallot), fruit (watermelon, orange, banana), occasional legumes, “city chicken” (*ayam bandar*), all their eggs, a few tins of canned food (sardines in particular), sea fish or beef on rare occasions, ingredients for cooking (coconut milk in bricks, dried anchovies, peanuts,

spices and herbs, salt, monosodium glutamate), tea, coffee, sugar, sweets and palm oil. The use of palm oil has considerably changed the villagers' diet and most dishes are now wok fried in a large amount of oil.

The current diet in the village consists of a mix of processed agro-industrial products, which are very high in calories and relatively low in nutrients, and local produce. Sugar is also consumed much more than before. Tea and coffee are made very sweet and are consumed at any time of the day, with or without unsweetened biscuits. Children frequently buy sweet snacks. It is likely that villagers, like the general Malaysian population, do not suffer from any major deficiencies, as is the case in poorer indigenous communities (*The Star* 2019), but have larger caloric intake than energy expenditure and a sugar intake that threatens them with type 2 diabetes and dental cavities. I do not have any statistics on the prevalence of this diabetes in Kampung Peta but it is part of the experience of the villagers who speak of it as a common condition. Type 2 diabetes affects about 20% of adults in Malaysia (Zanariah *et al.* 2015), perhaps less so in this village, where I noticed less overweight children than elsewhere in the country.

Another part of the food is produced on site, either self-produced or purchased from neighbours. "Here everyone has enough to eat²", says Syazrina, a women in her sixties. Most of the *kelamin* I have interviewed spend between RM 300 and 400 a month on food, which is one of their biggest expenses. Like other Malaysians, who enjoy a great abundance of food that plays an important role in social life, the Jakun of Kampung Peta generally have a varied diet at their disposal. As their income is unstable and fluctuating, they are able to adapt their expenses and can bring them down to about RM 50 per month, rice (the 10kg pack costs in 2019 RM 25-28) and basic food expenses (oil, anchovies, chilli pepper, garlic, shallots). The *lauk* (side dishes to be eaten with rice) is then reduced to the food available in the vicinity of the village: river fish and *pucuk* (wild leaves that are harvested for leisure as well as necessity). This is a strategy described to me by several people, including Asma: "If no money, you can go collect *pucuk paku*, you can go fishing, hunting, because you have the forest. (...) If you're lazy, you don't eat, *lah!*" Similarly, when there is not enough money to buy gas for cooking, her sister Iman says it is always possible to use wood gathered in the forest.

2 "Di sini semua makan cukup."

In the 1960s, cash income was used to acquire rice and goods (machetes, sarongs, crockery) but in the 1990s Shanthi Thambiah notes an expansion of the goods consumed.

For most families wage employment is the only means for acquiring processed food and new prestige symbols such as motorcycle, modern houses, electrical appliances, etc. (Thambiah 1999: 282)

Credit for a scooter or a car is as important an expense as food. Asma pays RM 380 in monthly instalments (*bulanan*) for her scooter, while a friend and her spouse pay a car loan of RM 450 each month, plus fuel. Modern lifestyle has increased equipment such as smart phones and the price of telecommunication for most people under 40. Salaries and income from the service sector make it easier to cover these expenses than the income of independent activities in the primary sector. This has contributed to making the service sector more attractive, as Shanthi Thambiah noted twenty years ago.

The desire for these new things has led to greater efforts on the part of men to find wage work and cash incomes, often with the result that the women became still more alone at home. The direct effect of this on the women is that they play a less important role for the family standard of living while the men became much more so as wage earners. (Thambiah 1999: 281)

In a village economy, with subsistence or commercial agriculture, women have their place in productive activities, but this is not the case in the context of wage employment. Economic trends and lifestyle hence change substantially the gender roles in the families.

4. INEQUALITIES BETWEEN WOMEN AND MEN IN THE LABOUR MARKET

Today there are four women and fifteen men employed at Taman Negara in Kampung Peta, two men employed at the Wildlife Conservation Society, one woman and five men employed in the palm plantations. One man and one woman are civil servants in Kampung Peta. Only in schools are there more women than men because employment is exclusively female in *tadika*. 26 men are employed in Kampung Peta, while only 10 women are.

	Women	Men
Taman Negara full-time	2	10
Taman Negara part-time	2	5
Public employment (school not included)	1	1
School (SK + tadika)	4	2
<i>Total public employment</i>	9	18
Wildlife Conservation Society	0	2
Plantation full-time	0	1
Plantation part-time	1	4
Other wage employment	0	1
<i>Total private employment</i>	1	8
Total	10	26

Table 2. Jakun people employed in Kampung Peta. My survey, spring 2019.

One of the reasons that are conducive of this situation may not be related to women's family obligations. Even though Jakun women can breastfeed their children up to age 5 or 6 (Maeda 2001: 66), other members of the extended family, mostly women but also men, can care for the offspring during their working hours, as I have observed. The most significant barrier to their employment is the discrimination they face from employers in hiring.

There is gender-based work-related discrimination in Malaysia. There is certainly a preference by most employers to hire men compared to women but women are preferred in certain professions. Women dominate in the public sector compared to the private sector. (Interview with Shanthi Thambiah, 16 August 2019)

Even in the public sector, women in Kampung Peta are half as likely as men to be employed, and inequalities explode in the private sector. There is no gender gap in Malaysia in the earnings of men and women in the public sector, but it is a reality in the private sector (Thambiah 2019). In their study on employment in Kampung Chang Lama (Perak) in the early 2000s, Colin Nicholas, Tijah Yok Chopil and Tiah Sabak observed different remuneration according to ethnicity and gender. Between 1970 and 1998, Orang Asli men are still paid half as much as non-Orang Asli men. The same gap is observed between Orang Asli and non-Orang Asli women (it was even greater in previous decades) and women are paid about a third less than men of the same ethnicity. The lower economic interest of women in

having a salaried position may also explain a priority within the *kelamin* for male employment, in a context where jobs are scarce and many people who are available for employment do not get one.

	Remuneration in 1970 (in RM)	Remuneration in 1998 (in RM)
Man non-OA	10	35
Man OA	5	18
Woman non-OA	8	25
Woman OA	2	12

Table 3. Wage trends of non-indigenous and indigenous workers in Kampung Chang Lama (Perak). Source: Colin Nicholas, Tijah Yok Chopil and Tiah Sabak 2003: 101.

Village women who are neither salaried nor self-employed in service activities may fall back, as men do, on self-entrepreneurship in the primary sector. They may also be *suri rumah*, or “queens of the house”, i.e. housewives. “A *suri rumah* implies a woman whose husband is sufficiently affluent that she need not concern herself with matters outside the domestic sphere” (Thompson 2012: 99). The concept of *suri rumah* suggests that women are not engaged in subsistence activities (gardening, collecting, fishing) nor do they share activities with their husbands, such as couples I observed who collect rattan and work on rubber farms together. Thompson insisted in his survey to know if his respondents were *suri rumah* or had a *kerja kampung* activity because the two options are mutually exclusive. In theory, the rural economy only considers inactive the people who are not able to work, which include dependent elderly people, children or pregnant women (for example a young married woman who was nearing term during my stay and had to stop all productive activity).

The concept of *suri rumah* originates from the city and is closer to the vision of the couple promoted by Islam (a man who rules at home and earns the household money) than to the more egalitarian gender relations of the Orang Asli. In Kampung Peta nine women are *suri rumah*, qualified as such by their husbands or by my informants whose first reflex was to tell me that they were “not working” (*tak kerja*). One of the husbands I interviewed expressed his pride that his wife was “*suri rumah sahaja*” and that his work as a fishing guide was enough for the whole family. The majority of these nine women have husbands who are employed, which is consistent with Thompson’s analysis that this model corresponds to the organisation of couples in which the man is a wage earner. However, some of these husbands work part-

time and at least one household in this situation is struggling to earn sufficient income to pay for their needs without the wife's participation. Two older women are also said to be *suri rumah* by my informant while their husbands *kerja kampung*, so they are most likely to help them. It seems to me that the concept of *suri rumah*, which is "not indigenous to the Orang Asli" (Thambiah 2019), was imported to the village before the effective generalization of the husband as the sole income earner. This confusion means that this model exists in representations before it exists in reality and this reflects a profound change in the way Orang Asli couples function.

This merging of indigenous social structures with those of the Malay majority is documented by other authors, whose work is cited by Nicholas *et al.* in their book on Semai women facing the degradation of the natural environment and the development of the market economy (Nicolas *et al.* 2003: 26-27). Signe Howell, referring to the Chewong group, notes that apart from employment opportunities open to men and closed to women, economic changes combined with unequal representations disrupt gender relations (Howell 1983: 46-47). Karen Endicott on Batek (1981) and Barbara Nowak on Mah Meri (1986) observed couples working together and a gendered specialisation of tasks that is not strict. A somewhat more recent survey conducted by Endicott and Endicott in 1990 documents a significant change in women's lifestyles in a community now engaged in agricultural activities.

One difference was that most women's activities took place in or near the camp. Women made few of the expeditions that had been so common before, in which large groups of women and children would go in the forest looking for food. With the increase of rice and flour in the diet, people sought wild tubers only as supplements or for special reasons. (Endicott et Endicott 2012: 210)

At the time of their first study in 1975-1976, "men in the farming group alternated between working on their fields and collecting forest produce for trade. (...) In 1990 hunting of all kinds had become almost exclusively a male occupation" (Endicott et Endicott 2012: 212).

According to these studies, the exclusion of women from productive work is due to the disappearance of mixed tasks, which is caused by the degradation or loss of the environment in which they were carried out. It is also caused by the attraction of an other lifestyle and other activities, in addition to discrimination against women in the labour market and the

assimilation of dominant representations of gender roles in society, particularly Muslim ones. Even the Jakun of Kampung Peta, who are animists and far more resistant to conversion to Islam than any other group in an other village, have endorsed the *suri rumah* model. This exclusion from productive activities has important implications on women's autonomy.

5. IMPLICATIONS FOR GENDER INEQUALITY

The first gendered specialisation of tasks among the Jakun was not accompanied by any coercion: "The wife and husband are equal, and neither seems to exercise authority over the other in any formal manner" (Maeda 2001: 65). Is this equality between spouses still on the agenda since the changes in the *kelamin* economy? Increased specialisation, where activities are allocated more strictly, with reproductive activities being allocated to women and productive activities to men only, has immediate repercussions on women's economic independence.

While some men have been compensated for the loss of their traditional livelihood, women have not been directly compensated in any way. In relinquishing their role in subsistence farming, the women have lost their economic independence to a certain degree. (Thambiah 1999 : 282)

During my survey, I have observed these differences in income between men and women: income from self-employment in the primary sector is due to the combined efforts of women and men, but almost always, when the couple benefits from additional income in wages and salaries or in services, it is solely the man's income (wage earners in Taman Negara and in free-lance tourism, wage employment in Kahang). When both spouses have this type of income, it is rare for the woman's income to be higher, but it does happen, as in the case of the *tadika* teacher. This difference in treatment in the labour market "may eventually lead to sexual inequalities, especially when the incomes earned by women are way below those earned by men" (Thambiah 1999: 284).

Iman, a young married woman, calls "staying at home" (*duduk di rumah sahaja*) a fate she personally considers unenviable. Since there is ultimately little work in a Jakun house in the absence of wood chores and subsistence activities, "women who have no children or only older children have little to do and are bored and restless" (Thambiah 1999: 281). This

situation impacts their well-being. The loss of economic independence of one of the spouses is also problematic in the couple: “Cash income increases the occasions for conflicts over how wages will be used” (*ibid.*). Men, who are under increased pressure to provide for the needs of the household, may fail and be left by their wives, sink into alcoholism or abandon their families (*ibid.*).

It is ironic that at a time when women are entering men’s sphere and are breaking out of the home and participating on a wider scale in areas previously considered men’s domains, the reverse is happening among the Orang Asli where men and women are beginning to experience segregation along sexual lines. (Thambiah 1999: 268)

Thambiah’s disturbing finding is mitigated by the fact that the Jakun maintain a “bilateral inheritance system” that does not deprive women of the means of production as is the case among the Malays, who give less inheritance to women. And we have seen that the trends she identified at the end of the 1990s were still not accomplished twenty years later, even though women have lower incomes overall than men and even though the existence in the village of women who “do not work” shows a devaluation of their contribution to household wealth. This concern is highlighted by an other fact, socio-economic inequalities between *kelamin*.

The spread of the notions of private property as belonging to only one family or one individual, either male or female, has denied access to resources they once had, especially where resources are becoming scarce. Variations in the status and position of women and men within the community accentuate the formation of economic classes. (Thambiah 1999: 287)

We will try to understand the extent to which these income inequalities break away from traditional uses and whether they are increasing over time.

6. OTHER INEQUALITIES AND HOW TO SLOW THEM DOWN

Among the Jakun, as in many Orang Asli communities, many resources are traditionally shared within the community. The land does not belong to anyone, its usufruct is offered in equal parts to each *kelamin* and the rice from the harvest is symbolically shared. Maeda calls

“moral order” and “technical order” the two registers in which the Jakun carry out the activities that enable them to earn a living. The first relates to subsistence activities in which the acquired goods must be shared to some extent. The second concerns goods of commercial value (even if they are the same goods, provided that they have a different circulation) and money.

It is the shift between moral exchanges and technical ones that appears to be an indicator of the direction of change. As technical exchanges increase within the hamlet, and as Orang Hulu [Jakun] begin to take exchanges of this sort as a matter of course, the distinction between the “rich” and the “poor” in the hamlet, a distinction which is hardly noticed or even made at present, may become clarified. (Maeda 2001 : 62)

From rattan remuneration to salaried employment, the market economy is changing social structures, whether it is equality between women and men or solidarity in the village. In the 1960s, it was frowned upon to appropriate a margin on a commercial activity, but in the 1990s, Jakun were now commonly employed as grocers and this appropriation was no longer considered problematic, reflecting a major change in the circulation of wealth. The obligation to share no longer applies to all activities, it is reduced to the immediate family, to certain goods or certain income (such as the lottery, which owes nothing to work and everything to luck). Everyone’s industry brings him or her an income that they are now free to keep for themselves or to share as they wish.

There are several causes for this shift. The village community of Kampung Peta has grown significantly. The land, which could be enjoyed by those who cultivated it, has become property and the object of trade (“commodification”, see Nonini 1992: 33-36), while the surface that can be cultivated by the Jakun has been reduced to a minimum. Furthermore, market economy has taken an increased importance in their life.

Within families, however, there is still some circulation of goods and services. The village has more inhabitants now and it results in these exchanges taking place in the closest family branches. Children who have an income contribute to sustaining their parents, whether they are elderly or caring for school-going children, so much so that few older people among my respondents receive the *Kebajikan Masyarakat*, an allowance of RM 300 or so allocated to

elderly people without resources. Young children move from house to house, spending their free time with their cousins. Women, who are often responsible for children because fathers are busy with other tasks, can always leave the care of their offspring to a sister or cousin.

Groups of people who eat together remain fairly flexible, it is not always the *kelamin* and there are many invitations between people from the same family. It is common to borrow (*tumpang, numpang*) various objects in this context: scooters are the ones that circulate in the most obvious way. The *kelamin* is therefore not the only area in which goods circulate, but the continuous exchange of gifts (“constant give and take”) no longer takes place at the village level, only at the level of the close family. There is a loosening of social interaction within the community as a whole.

7. INDIVIDUALISATION OF DESTINIES

The social organisation of the village and the reduction of “moral exchanges” do not smooth out the inequalities that increase in wages, hence Maeda’s concern that the generalisation of “technical exchanges” will lead to the formation of economic classes (Maeda 2001: 62). The land the village possesses is becoming too small for its population and not all *kelamin* have enough to live on. It results in disparities among all of them, which Colin Nicholas explains in a general history of land allocation in indigenous villages.

In the past, you work the land, the land is yours. Green paddy and so on. Once your activity ceases, the land goes back to the forest and to the community. But when the government came in with this policy of preservation and all this kind of things, they gave houses and lots. Specially rubber, each family a rubber lot, usually 6 acres per family (...). These lots became fixed. No more scope for expanding, no more new land. The first person gets 6 acres, but after that you have five children, you give all to one person or your divide by 5. It becomes smaller and smaller. After many generations, there is nothing to give up. (Interview with Colin Nicholas, 26 April 2019)

The collection of rattan in the forest makes it possible to cope with the lack of land, as well as the wage labour does. The income that everyone gets from one occupation or another is disparate: there are “rich” and “poor” people in the village and no redistribution mechanism

can reduce the gap between them. The villagers' discourses commenting on this situation often involve individual merit: those who earn enough are "smart" (*pandai*) or "hard-working" (*rajin*), the others are "stupid" (*bodoh*) or "lazy" (*malas*). In the event of failure, villagers are more likely to blame themselves than the economic situation: a woman whose grocery store went bankrupt during a closure of the Taman Negara, at a time when less money was circulating in Kampung Peta, says she failed because she was "lazy." Syazrina and her daughter Asma have very harsh words for a woman and her older husband, a cousin of Syazrina's who inherited two small plots of land and sold one to his sister. They say he is a lazy man who does not take responsibility for his large family. "She is nothing," says Asma about her during our survey of the village. Land is limited, but she says there are plenty of opportunities to get by. There is school, there is self-employment in agriculture or tourism, and at worst there is rattan and *pucuk*. She mentions several times the expression of Western tourists who have given her a life lesson: everyone is responsible for their own success or failure and it is this lesson that she delivers to a classmate who has to collect rattan with her husband since he lost his job on the plantation.

Zubaidah: When there's no food, we help each other in the village³.

Asma: You must go to work if you want something because nobody helps you, you make the responsibility your own.

Zubaidah: Not everyday people help you.

Asma: For everything you have the forest for sale. (Interview with Zubaidah.)

I observed that the options were limited for the villagers of Kampung Peta. Those who succeed in school have opportunities, provided they integrate into Malaysian urban society and do not stay in the village. Public jobs in the village are not for them but for the Malay majority. Only the *tadika* teacher has a qualified job that matches her level of education. She says she takes advantage of the fact that her Malay colleagues are not interested in the location of the job. The other graduates have to leave the village or remain in the village without opportunity (a tourist guide has a background in accountancy and the wife of a rubber farmer has a bachelor's degree in political science from Universiti Sains Malaysia). They are all under 40 years old, which suggests that these school and university opportunities are fairly recent. Despite these constraints, Asma relies on individual merit and is very pessimistic about the possibility of having a collective destiny.

3 "Kalau tak ada makan, kampung tolong-tolong."

I have a principle. If you want to succeed in life, don't wait for anyone. I think we're alone in life. One day we won't be together with Mother, we won't always live with our friends, sometimes we need to make our own life⁴. (Interview with Asma)

Paradoxically, Asma is one of the persons most involved in the life of the village and particularly in projects coming from outside the village: she participates in the indigenous community conservation programme (ICCA) of United Nations Development Programme and is the village referent for the NGO Gerai OA which helps Orang Asli women to produce and sell handicrafts (even if she herself does not produce any). She therefore navigates between two registers: the responsibility of the individual and the apprehension of the village as a social entity capable of carrying out together the collective initiatives proposed from the outside – because it is always in a collective register that these initiatives are formulated. Colin Nicholas proposes to carry out these projects without any illusion on the motivation (according to him very mixed) for the common good: “Nobody works for free,” he says, but he does not despair of the village's capacity to organise itself collectively. The lack of effectiveness of the initiatives that have been carried out so far is due only to epiphenomena. “The community is united but it's not organised. Wrong people were given responsibility” (interview with Colin Nicholas). He therefore proposes structures that are partly community-based and partly private, from which the people maintaining them and the community remaining in control would both benefit. Individual self-interest could, in his view, contribute to the effectiveness of these structures better than volunteering.

Jakun society remains structurally egalitarian, with equal participation of everyone in collective decisions, but it is evolving into an unequal society in which individualism and individual choices and actions are becoming the norm. The Kampung Peta community is unique in that environmental degradation has little or no impact on it, and unlike other Orang Asli communities it is only deprived of the forest through legal provisions. However, similar changes can be observed in other Orang Asli villages and groups facing different situations: the Temiar (Nobuta 2009), the Semai (Gomes 2004 and Nicholas *et al.* 2003), the Batek (Endicott and Endicott 2012), to name but a few studies focused on economy. These

4 “Saya ada prinsip. Kalau mau berjaya, jangan tunggu orang. Saya percaya kita ada life sendiri. One day kita not always together dengan Mak, kita tak selalu hidup dengan kawan, sometimes kita perlu ada kehidupan sendiri.”

developments have been driven by structural economic changes and the extension of the market economy into rural communities, changes that have also disrupted Malay village communities (Scott 2008). These changes, sometimes disruptions, may be experienced positively (access to consumer goods, richer food) or as a loss, especially when it comes to cultural transformations. Development, as well as tourism, is an ambiguous blessing.

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